

Methodology of Human Capital Evaluation System at the Macro Level

Žiedūna Liepė^a *

^a*Kaunas University of Technology, Donelaicio str. 73, Kaunas LT-44029, Lithuania*

Abstract

The development of human capital (HC) has a special, non-liquid value that provides the economy with the potential to grow and with the new status of being. Therefore in evaluation of HC in macro level, it is very important to assess properly the factors affecting the formation of HC value. This paper presents a methodology of HC evaluation system in macro level which is based on the creation of comparative database of HC structure among the countries, on the estimation of HC value, distinguishing four constituents and on the evaluation of HC utilization efficiency in the value creation process. Findings reveal that estimation of HC value uncloze an access to the calculation of net HC value, meanwhile, comparison of HC systems and its utilization efficiency are more related with the application of the estimated HC value.

© 2013 AARESOC.

Keywords: Human capital, human capital value, human capital evaluation, human capital evaluation system, utilization of human capital;

1. Introduction

The concept of HC for economic science is known for at least the last fifty years (Schultz, 1964; Becker, 1964), although its origins can be found in the works of W. Petty in XVII century.

In the economic theories of present day it is recognized the role of HC and the necessity of its management, including public policy measures. This challenges the need to understand the formation and utilization of HC as a manageable process, which has to be well acknowledged both in micro and in macro level.

It should be noted that most of the theoretical and practical achievements are made in works, dealing with the problems of HC in enterprise level. Questions on how to measure, monitor and effectively manage the HC in order to develop and enhance corporate value, were analyzed by Mayo (2001), Baron and Armstrong (2007), Coco, Jamison and Black, (2011), who highlighted people as creating value rather than cost or source of expense. The role of investment in HC on organization's success, highlighting the HC management aspects were researched by AL-Ma'ani & Jaradat (2010), Murray & Efendioglu (2007), Schwarz & Murphy (2008). Such authors as DiBernardino (2011), Fitz-enz (2009), Schuler (2004), Scholz, Stein and Bechtel (2004) have analyzed the problems and methods of HC evaluation.

Analyzing the HC problems at the macroeconomic level, it is a significant contribution of such authors as Wei (2003), Nafukho, Hairston & Brooks (2004), Arrazola & Hevia (2008), You (2009), Erosa, Koreshkova & Restuccia (2010) Kagochi & Jolly (2010), Tudorescu & Zaharia (2011), highlighting the common philosophy of HC impact on economic growth, national competitiveness increase. The comprehensive researches of HC impact on performance results among branches were carried out by Kleynhans (2006), Doong, Fung & Wu (2011), Boedker, Mouritsen & Guthrie (2008), Baier, Dwyer and Tamura (2006). But macroeconomic level is usually restricted by retrieval of the relationship between HC and performance indicators, moreover HC itself still is not explicitly expressed in terms of value, the most commonly are used single indicators such as wage rates, number of employees, etc.

* Žiedūna Liepė Tel.: +370-687-63925

E-mail address: zieduna.liepe@ktu.lt

[Type text]

The purpose of the article is to present a methodology of HC evaluation system in macro level. The research methods used were the detailed analysis and synthesis of scientific literature, the exploratory multivariate factor - indices analysis of descriptive statistics and correlative regression analysis.

2. Elements of human capital evaluation system in macro level

HC formation and evaluation is not a self-sustaining process. Its creation requires large capital investments - financial, material and time input, which has to pay off over a longer or shorter period of time and which depends on the internal and external environmental conditions.

The HC evaluation goals and methods used in macro level determine several variants of HC value calculation, which allow distinguishing the elements of HC evaluation system (see Fig. 1). Despite the peculiarities of HC evaluation system calculation, which are reflected in the evaluation methodology of the individual elements, there are also some general features common to them all.

Figure 1. Elements of human capital evaluation system in macro level

Evaluation of HC value by the wage and formation value (cost) shows the access to the calculation of net HC value. Meanwhile, identification of HC structure and evaluation of HC utilization efficiency are more related with the application of estimated HC value. HC value depends not only on the formation or consuming value, but also on the level of material and financial funds, labor and the production organization, innovation and so on.

2.1. Identification of human capital structure

The first element of HC evaluation system (see Fig. 1) involves a method of HC structure identification, indicating the key socio - economic indicators that form the HC value, grouping them into the partial and a complex HC value index and creating an information base for HC structure comparison.

HC structure evaluation in macro-level functions to some certain restrictions:

1. The HC structure evaluation must include not only the direct evaluation of HC, but also the HC environmental assessment. This is a broader concept than the HC evaluation in monetary units.

2. The objective of HC structure evaluation is to form the necessary base of adjuvant indicators for HC assessment.

3. The HC evaluation reliability is determined by the level of statistical system, talking of the HC system research in EU countries, its reliability depends on the data level published by Eurostat.

HC structure evaluation framework of individual country consists of a number of social and economic indicators, which, depending on its size and system performance are expressed in various sizes of absolute or relative indicators that need to be brought together in a comparative framework. An accomplished analysis of mathematical and statistical (Bartoseviciene, 2010) methods applied for these objectives disclosed, that the best way to reach these goals is to apply a multi-factor indices method.

The calculation of the complex HC value index and it's statistical reliability was performed by the following seven stages (see Fig. 2).

Figure 2. Formation process stages of the complex HC value index

In the 1st stage was formed the data base, which consists of the European Union countries data published in the Eurostat, World Data Bank statistical data basis and the Human Development reports (Eurostat, 2010; World data band, 2011; Human development report, 2011). In order to reduce the data size influence on the calculation of the results there was performed the normalization of indicators: instead of the absolute values was used the growth coefficient / percentage or was calculated the value of absolute indicator per inhabitant / employee. The formed database was processed using SPSS package program support.

In the 2nd stage was estimated the variance of the analyzed data, checking the data correlation with each other and identifying the affinities. If there are no such affinities then further factor analysis would be meaningless. Formed inter-correlation matrix of the analyzed indicators allowed to reduce the scope of the database, eliminating the indicators weakly correlated with each other or logically related indicators strongly correlated with each other.

In the 3rd stage were determined the missing countries data using the S - mean procedure - which involves the calculation of missing rows data using the average method. This allowed maintaining certain variables for the calculation, without changing its position relative to others.

In the 4th stage, using N-tile procedures was carried out the data scale alignment. This allowed in calculations to use the indicators in different measures, for example, fertility rate is measured in percentage, the population change - in units, life expectancy - in year's, gross domestic product in thousands of Euro, etc. Using N-tile procedure, the variables were grouped into five segments (1 - the lowest value and 5 - the highest value).

In 5th stage there was calculated the statistical validity[†] of HC system indices using the factor analysis and multicollinearity[‡] was tested using reliability analysis. If validity demonstrates the compliance of the research with its stated objectives, reliability (or consistency) is a methodological characteristic, showing the degree of measurement accuracy (Garson, 2009). During the research, reliability analysis was accomplished using the internal consistency method, which is based on the correlation of individual variables that make up the overall group, using Cronbach's alpha model, which evaluates whether all the scales variables adequately reflect the size of exploration.

In the 6th stage was accomplished the country's ranking according to the estimates of HC index value ranges, taking into account their deviation from the average, for the conversions using the standard normal distribution Z - scale.

[†] *Validity* – the degree to which survey measures what it is supposed to measure and the relationship among variables based on the data are correct or 'reasonable' (Garson, 2009).

[‡] *Multicollinearity* - a strong linear relationship among two or more independent variables (Garson, 2009).

[Type text]

Standardization converts the key data to a common scale of a normal distribution, when the mean is equal to - 0 and a standard deviation - 1 (Groh, Liechtenstein, Lieser, 2009). Thus, the variables with exceptional values have a great impact on other indicators.

In the 7th stage were distinguished groups of the EU countries. Purpose of this analysis – to group objects, so that the differences within the group would be minimal, while between the groups - the larger. Groups were formed by using the simplest and most commonly used in practice k - mean method, which disaggregates data into k groups.

For the HC structure comparative analysis there was formed an indices calculation system, involving these levels:

- in the highest level is calculated a complex HC value index;
- a complex index consist from five complex sub-indices: HC social value index; HC innovation index; HC economic value index; HC cost index; HC income value index;
- in the lowest level are found the indices of individual indicators.

The primary database analysis was based on correlation strength among the indicators. For the empirical study were selected indicators strongly correlated with the HC value, they were combined with each other by organizing and integrating them into one complex index of HC value.

2.2. Estimation of human capital value in macro level

The estimation of HC value is based on the alignment of two elements of HC evaluation system in macro level (see Fig. 1) - HC wage value and HC formation and investment value. Here for calculation of HC value in monetary terms there are distinguished four constituents: 1) HC value base; 2) HC value depreciation; 3) HC value recovery; 4) HC value alteration due to the level of motivation.

The implementation of HC systemic evaluation technique in macro level was guided by the following key principles.

The market is affected by specific labor market laws, supported by the wage assessment of employees in economy labor market. Actually paid wages can not always guarantee the retention of a skilled workforce, so there is a need to evaluate the role of the difference between the actual and the required wage for the pursued objectives solution.

HC evaluation has to ensure the dynamic aspect of the evaluation process. However, an evaluation of the HC value development is possible only when you can calculate the value of HC in a certain moment of time – during a year. After an estimation of HC value at a given time, you can continue with the dynamic assessment of HC value.

HC value in macro-level involves the value of the employees' whole knowledge, skills and abilities for the long-term value creation process guarantee. In this sense, the country's employed population covers the foundation of HC value. It is necessary to realize that the value creation process is in a constantly changing environment therefore an ongoing knowledge development is a necessary condition of the modern society. The depreciation of knowledge can not be ignored, accordingly it can not be measured solely the basic education, there should be permanent, additional investments, in order to update existing and acquire new knowledge. Knowledge maintenance and development rates of the most are influenced by the technological development rate. There is no explicit dependence of knowledge depreciation from time: slower of faster uniform level of knowledge depreciation is changed by the volcanic demand periods for new knowledge. Thus, the need for knowledge - leads to the value of knowledge: the available knowledge may become useless by the change of priorities importance of knowledge in the value creation process. Therefore HC value compensation is important not only for the company, but also for the whole economy level.

For the HC value estimation in macro-level there has been adapted the formula of “Saarbruecken” applied for calculation of HC value in the enterprise level (Scholz, Stein, Bechtel, 2004), distinguishing the four constituents of HC value in macro-level:

- HC value base (HC_b), which includes the wages of country's employees and social security contributions, with the adjustment of purchasing power parity level in the country;
- HC value depreciation (HC_d) due to actual aging of employees' knowledge;
- HC value recovery (HC_r), is documented as an increase of knowledge because of human resources training and development;
- HC value alteration (HC_a) evaluates the possible changes because of motivation, innovation and organizational level.

$$HC_v = HC_b - HC_d + HC_r + HC_a \quad (1)$$

here HC_v – HC value; HC_b – HC value base; HC_d – HC value depreciation; HC_r – HC value recovery; HC_a – HC value alteration.

It can be argued that a well-motivated team, which have and systematically maintain relevant for value creation knowledge, in turn creates a high value of HC. Although the logic of equation (1) correspond to the HC value calculation in the enterprise level, but the calculation of individual elements of the equation has significant differences that need to be detailed.

HC value base consist of employees' wage that reflects their skills and leverage the conditions of market wage amount. Here are evaluated the contributions for social insurance, which indirectly corresponds to wage: by the change of compulsory social insurance contributions, usually change the payments from wages for learning, treatment and so on.

Employee's wages and contributions for social insurance may be calculated in different ways: in aggregated - the average wage per employee multiplying by the number of employees; in detailed – calculating this indicator on the basis of workers education level, occupation, by the number of employees working in certain sectors of the economy, and the like. The particularity of calculation is determined by the existing level of each country's government statistics. As a rule, the statistics of an individual government greatly increases the imagery of calculation results and interpretive opportunities, however, the need to ensure comparability among the countries is inseparable from the calculation particularity reduction. In the database of Eurostat statistics there was selected an indicator meeting the evaluation objectives – wages for employees, including employers' social contributions in Euros.

Considering the level of wages among the individual countries, it is necessary to evaluate not only the nominal wage, but also the fact that in several countries the purchasing power even of the same currency is uneven. It is therefore necessary to evaluate these variations in the purchasing power of each country. Purchasing power parity calculated for consumption goods is given in the database of Eurostat statistics, and after the appropriate adjustments can be used for wage base harmonization in the EU. In the simplest form the parity of consumption value include the relative price levels, which show the same level of goods or services in the national currency of different countries.

In determining the **HC value loss** due to the real depreciation of employees' knowledge, there emerge a number of problems, the solution of which in the modern knowledge society era would allow a fresh look at evaluation of HC in macro-level.

HC value depreciation is calculated evaluating the process of employees' actual knowledge aging. Knowledge depreciation rate is calculated indirectly, using the influencing factors innovation indexes and determining the coefficients of knowledge devaluation.

Knowledge depreciation rates indirectly are reflected by such innovation indices:

- An index of high-tech exports as a percentage of the total export amount;
- An index of the number of patents per one million inhabitants;
- An index of expenditure on information technology as a percentage of GDP;
- An index of expenditure on research and experimental activities as a percentage of GDP;

Each index can vary from 0 to 5. The weighted average of three indices gives an average value, which is used for knowledge "depreciation" coefficient identification. The index is higher, the depreciation is more intense, and accordingly the depreciation rate is higher. To determine the knowledge depreciation coefficient is used the linear relationship and it can be expressed by the equation (2):

$$C_{kd} = I_n \times 0,2 \quad (2)$$

Accordingly HC value depreciation (see equation 3) is calculated:

$$HC_d = HC_v \times C_{kd} \quad (3)$$

HC value recovery can be realized in several ways:

1. by replacing the employees with lost qualification by highly skilled employees from other organizations or even other countries (this conversion option is limited);
2. by attracting new professionals from higher educational institutions;
3. by organizing staff training and re-training;
4. by raising skills independently.

In practice all the methods are used, but the main component that provides recovery of lost knowledge - graduates of various educational institutions and training and re-training. In the level of individual country the indicators from Eurostat statistics database reflecting these factors allows to calculate the absolute values of expenditure on education and training.

The quantity of HC value recovery in macro level was determined directly by the selection of two indicators:

- General public expenditure on education (all education levels from 0 to 6) as a percentage of GDP;
- Investment in skills upgrading and retraining, as a percentage of GDP.

HC value alteration or an increase is determined by the variable level of employees' motivation. Motivation level coefficient has to reflect the impact on the HC value of the employees' wishes and will to work, an effective social interaction and communication structure. The quantitative level of motivation is calculated in the base of motivation index, using the methodology applied for the calculation of the knowledge depreciation.

Calculating the HC value alteration, the motivation and country's organization level was associated with the organizational and innovative level indices:

- Human development index;
- Life-long learning - participation in training index, 15-64 years age group.

Selection of these indicators is based on the fact that evaluation of the individual countries based on these indicators indirectly indicates a motivation level of each country's people to seek for new knowledge, learn, and thus cause the country's well-being.

2.3. Evaluation of human capital utilization efficiency

In this part it is realized the last element of the HC evaluation system (see Fig. 1) - evaluation of HC utilization efficiency, assessing the role of the HC in the value creation process in relation with the overall EU economic indicators.

Today, we undoubtedly accept the argument that "people is everything", "human capital is the most important capital" (Hitt, Duane, 2002). In practice, however, success has been achieved in those countries that have exceptional natural resources and high-tech level material base. This does not mean that it can be denied the role of HC in economic development, but it must be justified by economic calculations.

Judging about the country's achieved economic results, it is important to choose an optimal situation reflecting indicators – or system of indicators (indicators selection was determined by statistical data availability). The study aims to clarify the relationship between the result achieved (Y) and its affecting factors (X_1, \dots, X_n):

$$Y = f(X_1, X_2, \dots, X_n) \quad (4)$$

It was performed a logical justification of investigated factors (see equation 4), determining these indicators, affecting the country's performance (GDP): HC value (X_1); gross fixed capital formation, including intangible assets (X_2); and consumed materials value in the country (X_3), all of them expressed in millions of Euro.

Generally, the evaluation of human capital utilization efficiency involving the correlation - regression analysis is performed by the following steps:

- It is carried out a logical justification of investigated factors (see equation 4), i.e. what factors logically reflect the analysis process and should be included into the multiple regression equation;
- It is applied a regression and correlation analysis of the factors in order to identify the existence of the linear dependence among the selected indicators. For this purpose, it is used a matrix of Pearson's correlation coefficients and partial correlation coefficients;
- It is calculated an equation of multiple linear regression;
- It is carried out an interpretation of obtained estimates during the statistical analysis.

Acknowledgements

This article presented a methodology of human capital evaluation system in macro level which allowed determining several elements that are based on:

- Identification of HC structure by calculation of complex HC value index and creation of comparative database among the countries and verification of its effectiveness, using a factor - indices analysis and clustering methods;

- Estimation of HC value, by the alignment of HC wage value and HC formation – investment value, distinguishing four constituents: 1) real wage amount, evaluating purchasing power parity; 2) knowledge loss in value terms; 3) knowledge loss recovery; 4) HC values increase due to the level of motivation;
- Evaluation of HC operation efficiency by the rate of HC utilization in the value creation process, distinguishing the overall economic indicators.

An empirical application of the presented methodology would allow to perform a systemic evaluation of HC in the individual countries by the identification of their HC structure and evaluation of the level of different factors development, providing the directions for growth and measures for detected drawback elimination. The estimation of HC value in monetary terms, based on the indicated constituents of HC value, allows calculating the comparative HC value in macro-level.

References

- AL-Ma'ani, A. I. & Jaradat, N. (2010). Impact of Human Capital on the Organization Performance. *Interdisciplinary Journal of Contemporary Research in Business*, 2 (4), 63-73.
- Arrazola, M. & Hevia, J. (2008). Three measures of returns to education: An illustration for the case of Spain. *Economics of Education Review*, Volume 27, Issue 3, June 2008, P. 266–275.
- Baier, S., Dwyer, G., Tamura, R. (2006). How important are capital and total factor productivity for economic growth? *Economic Inquiry*, 44(1), 23-50.
- Baron, A., & Armstrong, M. (2007). *Human capital management: achieving added value through people*. London: Kogan Page Limited.
- Bartoseviciene, V. (2010). *Ekonomines statistikos pagrindai*. Mokomoji knyga. Kaunas: Technologija, p. 97-104.
- Becker, G. (1962). Investment in human capital: A theoretical analysis. *Journal of Political Economy*, 70, 9-49.
- Boedker, Ch., Mouritsen, J., Guthrie, J. (2008). Enhanced business reporting: international trends and possible policy directions. *Journal of Human Resource Costing & Accounting*, Vol. 12 Iss: 1, pp.14 – 25
- Coco, C. T., Jamison, F. & Black, H. (2011). Connecting People Investments and Business Outcomes at Lowe's: Using Value Linkage Analytics to Link Employee Engagement to Business Performance. *People & Strategy*, Volume 34, Issue 2, 28-33.
- DiBernardino, F. (2011). The Missing Link: Measuring and Managing Financial Performance of the Human Capital Investment. *People & Strategy*, Volume 34, Issue 2, 44-49.
- Doong, S. H., Fung, H. G., & Wu, J., Y. (2011). Are social, financial, and human capital value enhancing? Evidence from Taiwanese firms. *International Review of Economics & Finance*, Volume 20, Issue 3, June 2011, Pages 395–405.
- Erosa, A., Koreschkova, T., Restuccia, D. (2010). How Important Is Human Capital? A Quantitative Theory Assessment of World Income Inequality. *Review of Economic Studies*, Volume 77, Issue 4, p. 1421-1449.
- Eurostat (2010). *European Commission „Eurostat“ information*. Retrieved March 11, 2012, from http://appsso.eurostat.ec.europa.eu/nui/show.do?dataset=mny_stk_mcp_a&lang=en.
- Fitz-enz, J. (2009). *The ROI of Human Capital: Measuring the Economic Value of Employee Performance*. New York, Amacom.
- Garson, G. D. (2009). *Factor Analysis. Topics in Multivariate Analysis*. Retrieved May 20, 2012, from <http://www2.chass.ncsu.edu/garson/pa765/statnote.htm>
- Groh, A. P., Liechtenstein, H.V., & Lieser, K. (2009). *The European venture capital and private equity country attractiveness index(es)*. IESE Business School – University of Navarra, p. 1- 15.
- Hitt, M. A., & Duane, R. (2002). The Essence of Strategic Leadership: Managing Human and Social Capital. *Journal of Leadership & Organizational Studies*, Vol. 9, No. 1.
- Human development report (2011). *The human development index report information*. Retrieved March 25, 2012, from http://hdr.undp.org/en/media/HDR_2010_EN_TechNotes_reprint.pdf
- Kagochi, J. M. & Jolly, C. M. (2010). R&D Investments, Human Capital, and the Competitiveness of Selected U.S. Agricultural Export Commodities. *International Journal of applied Economics*, 7(1), 58-77.
- Kleynhans, E. P. J. (2006). The Role of Human Capital in the Competitive Platform of South African Industries. *SA Journal of Human Resource Management*, 4, 55-62.
- Mayo, A. (2001). *The human value of the enterprise. Valuing people as assets – monitoring, measuring, managing*. London: Nicholas Brealey Publishing.
- Murray, L. W., & Efendioglu, A. M. (2007). Valuing the investment in organizational training. *Industrial and Commercial training*, Vol. 39, No. 7, 372-379.
- Nafukho, F. M., Hairston, N. R. & Brooks, K. (2004). Human capital theory: Implications for human resource development. *Human Resource Development International*, 7 (4), 545 -551.
- Scholz, Ch., Stein, V., & Bechtel, R. (2004). *Human Capital Management*. Wege aus der Unverbindlichkeit Walters Kluwer Deutschland GmbH, Munchen. Unterschleisheim.
- Schuller, T. (2004). Three Capitals: A Framework. T. Schuller, J. Preston, C. Hammond, A. Brassett-Grundy & j. Bynner (eds.). *The Benefits of Learning: The Impact of Education on Health, Family Life and Social Capital*. London: RoutledgeFalmer, 12-33.

- Schultz, T. W. (1964). *Investment in Human Capital*. Economic Growth – an American problem, Englewood Cliffs.
- Schwarz, J. L., & Murphy, T. E. (2008). Human capital metrics: an approach to teaching using data and metrics to design and evaluate management practices. *Journal of management education*, Vol. 32, No. 2, 164-182.
- Tudorescu, N. & Zaharia, C. (2011). Human Capital Accumulation and Long Run Economic Growth. *Journal of Economics, Management, and Financial Markets*. Volume: 5(4) , 250-255.
- Wei, H. (2003). *Measuring the stock of human capital for Australia*. Working paper, Australian Bureau of Statistics, Canberra.
- World data bank (2011). „*The world bank*“ information. Retrieved April 8, 2012, from <http://data.worldbank.org/indicator/FP.CPI.TOTL.ZG>
- You, H. (2009). *The Contribution of Rising School Quality to U.S. Economic Growth*. Manuscript, SUNY Bualo.